

X-Ray Edge Absorption Coefficients and Covalency of Bonding[†]

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A method has been suggested for measurement of covalency of bonding using X-ray edge absorption coefficients. Expressions have been derived which emphasise the role of screening by electrons involved in covalent bonding. Usefulness of the method in understanding bonding in a few glasses has been illustrated. Use of higher initial quantum states in edge absorption studies has been shown to give rise to higher sensitivity of absorption coefficients to covalency effect.

COHESION in solids arises from different types of bonding¹. Among these ionic covalent and metallic types of bonding give rise to large cohesive energies compared to van der Waals and hydrogen bond types. In many solids, cohesion arises from more than one type of bonding. The structure and stability of solids are determined by the details of such bonding. Thus, close packed structures are common in metals and large coordinations occur in ionic solids. Similarly, more open low coordination structure of covalent solids is a consequence of directionality of bonding in them. Melting and solid state polymorphism can also be directly related to the nature of interaction potentials in these materials². Hence, one of the primary concerns of physical chemistry is to understand the nature of bonding in solids in sufficient detail.

The need to understand the nature of bonding becomes even more acute in amorphous solids because here, one finds very often the same chemical compound existing with and without long-range order. With the loss of long-range order, the temperature ranges of stability of the glasses decrease to almost two-thirds or less³ (the glass transition temperature, T_g is approximately equal to two-thirds of the melting temperature, T_m). Further, the specific volumes of glasses are also generally higher than those of corresponding crystalline solids. Combined with the observation that covalently bonded materials are usually good glass formers³, the above features make it appear quite probable that the bonding in glasses is more covalent. Increase in covalency introduces a directionality in bonding and reduction in the coordination number. Increased covalency is often associated with a shrinkage in the inter-atomic distances which increases the cohesive energy arising from the near-neighbour interactions^{4,5}. This conditioning of the nature of bonding in amorphous solids is an important subject to study in order to understand the glassy state.

This work is confined to a consideration of the ionic-covalent bond duality which pervades a very large part of inorganic solids. Many attempts have been made to relate quantitatively the extent of ionicity of a bond to chemical parameters, like electronegativity differences, *etc.*^{6,7}. But ionicity estimates are very difficult to obtain experimentally. Several methods have been discussed in the literature⁸⁻¹⁰. But the applicability of these methods become quite restricted since they are generally based on measurement of magnetic properties or optical transitions arising in transition-metal ions. It has now been found that a suitable experimental method is provided by X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS). Materials with ionic-covalent mixed types of bonding may be investigated by an analysis of the absorption coefficients of the edges in XAS. This paper describes briefly an analysis of covalency effect using absorption coefficients in XAS. Some examples from the author's investigations are presented where the method appears quite promising.

Covalency also causes chemical shifts in edge energies^{11,12}. But the analysis of chemical shifts can be quite complicated¹³ and is unsuitable when covalency effects are marginal.

Principles of XAS :

X-ray spectroscopy consists of measuring X-ray absorption coefficients as a function of proton energy. Sudden jumps in absorption coefficients occur at the absorption edges (Fig. 1) due to the excitation of core electrons. Well above the edge, the absorption coefficients decay and is associated with intensity modulations described as Extended X-ray Absorption Fine Structure (EXAFS)¹⁴. This region consists of valuable structural information which, however, is not discussed in this article. Absorption coefficient variations are also present at the edges also upto ~ 30 eV above the edge and are described as X-ray Absorption Near Edge Structure (XANES).

[†] Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

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Fig. 1. A typical X-ray absorption spectrum associated with the $L_{2,3}$ -edge of Th in crystalline ThF_4 . The spectrum is unnormalised.

The origin of XANES is quite simply excitation of core electrons to available unoccupied energy levels which may have atomic or molecular character^{15,16}. Unoccupied final states of very high energies (well above the bonding states) often correspond to extended states and electrons in such levels undergo multiple scattering from neighbouring atoms which affects the spectral features. Such effects are both complicated and poorly understood¹⁷. The features closely associated with the absorption edge are a result of excitations to localised bound states and may, therefore, be treated as core electron spectrum. Excitations are governed by the selection rules of atomic and molecular spectroscopy. With conventional X-ray sources edge spectra can be obtained quite easily at energies corresponding to K-edges of elements like Ti and above. But with the advent of synchrotron radiation, sufficiently good spectra can be obtained even for edges requiring photons of 7-8 Å wavelength. It enables study of K-edges of elements such as aluminium and silicon. With heavier elements (such as silver and beyond), it is convenient to study the L-edge spectra. Rare-earth L-edges are particularly suitable for investigation with most X-ray sources. Though much less has been reported in the literature on M-edge spectra, M-edges of heavier elements, like thallium, bismuth, lead, etc. should in principle be easy to investigate. X-ray spectra are recorded straight as absorption coefficients in synchrotron based work which are further normalised using experimental edge jumps¹⁴.

Absorption coefficients and effect of covalency :

In general, the absorption coefficient corresponding to such an edge is given by¹⁸

$$\mu = \frac{4\pi e^2}{n^2 c} |M_{if}|^2 \delta(E_i - E_f - \hbar\omega) \quad (1)$$

where, n is the refractive index, E_i and E_f are the energies of the initial and final states, respectively, ω is the circular frequency of the photon, δ is Kronecker's delta and M_{if} is the dipole matrix element (defined further later). The expression is derived on the basis of one electron approximation and Koopman suddenness criterion. In further discussions, we assume the applicability of equation (1). M_{if} is given by the expression,

$$M_{if} = \langle i | r_a | f \rangle \quad (2)$$

where, $\langle i |$ and $| f \rangle$ are the initial and final state wave functions, respectively. One can, therefore, theoretically evaluate the absorption coefficients, provided suitable wave functions are available. In the present context where we investigate the variation of bonding nature, approximate wave functions, such as Slater orbitals may be employed without serious prejudice to the basic objective.

Absorption coefficients are affected significantly when the final state wave functions are affected as may be easily seen from equations (1) and (2). The final states are affected when the nature of bonding is altered because such changes remove or reinforce electron density in the final state. When the final state is a valence state directly involved in bonding, the effect is quite obvious. But when the final state is a vacant orbital not involved in bonding, the variation in electron density in the bonding orbital alters the screening of the final state which in turn affects M_{if} . The first situation is illustrated by some transition metal complexes where the bonding states are themselves final states in $L_{2,3}$ -edge spectra. The absorption coefficients are determined by vacancies in the d-orbitals which vary according to the nature of ligands. But the situation arising from screening of the final states is particularly valuable in the study of bond-ionicity variations which we exploit further in the following.

Let us consider a completely ionic complex with an $M^{n+} A^{b-}$ bond. Further, that the valence levels involved in the M-L bonding are ns and np (n is the principal quantum number). The associated $L_{2,3}$ -spectra make use of vacant nd levels for $| f \rangle$. When A is substituted by a less electronegative ligand A' , the M-A' bond becomes slightly covalent. As a consequence of this a small electron density may be considered to have been brought back to ns, np levels of M . This alters the screening of nd levels which affects $| f \rangle$ and M_{if} . Let us suppose ν electrons are added back to ns, np levels by covalency. We can estimate the effect of this on M_{if} by using appropriately screened wave func-

tion for $|f\rangle$ (and also for $|i\rangle$) in the form,

$$|f\rangle, (|i\rangle) = (r^{n_f^* - 1}) \exp[(z - s_f) r / n_f^*] \quad (3)$$

$$(\mu_{cov} / \mu_{ion}) = |M_{if}|_{cov}^2 / |M_{if}|_{ion}^2 \quad (4)$$

where, μ_{ion} and μ_{cov} are absorption coefficients corresponding to purely ionic and partially covalent situations, respectively.

$$|M_{if}|_{ion} = \int_0^\infty [r^{n_f^* - 1} e^{(z - s_f)r / n_f^*}] \cdot r \cdot [r^{n_i^* - 1} e^{(z - s_i)r / n_i^*}] dr \quad (5)$$

with a similar expression for $|M_{if}|_{cov}$. The quantities in equation (5) can be simplified with the following substitutions,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} (n_f^* + n_i^* - 1) &= n_s \\ z(1/n_f^* + 1/n_i^*) &= Z_s \\ (s_f/n_f^* + s_i/n_i^*) &= S_s \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

Equation (5) may now be written as

$$|M_{if}|_{ion} = \int_0^\infty r^{n_s} \cdot e^{(Z_s - S_s)r} dr$$

and

$$|M_{if}|_{cov} = \int_0^\infty r^{n_s} \cdot e^{(Z_s - S'_s)r} dr \quad (7)$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{|M_{if}|_{cov}^2}{|M_{if}|_{ion}^2} &= \frac{\Gamma(n_s + 1) / (Z_s - S'_s)^{n_s + 1}}{\Gamma(n_s + 1) / (Z_s - S_s)^{n_s + 1}} \\ &= \left(\frac{Z_s - S_s}{Z_s - S'_s} \right)^{2n_s + 2} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where, $\Gamma(x)$ are Gamma functions. S'_s is higher than S_s because of the screening caused by the electrons responsible for covalent bonding. S_s and S'_s are related as

$$S'_s = S_s + \frac{\nu \times 0.35}{n_f^*}$$

where, ν is the number of covalency electrons added to ns, np levels. Hence, equation (8) becomes

$$\frac{|M_{if}|_{cov}^2}{|M_{if}|_{ion}^2} = \left(\frac{Z_s - S_s}{Z_s - S_s - 0.35\nu/n_f^*} \right)^{2n_s + 2} \quad (9)$$

Since $(Z_s - S_s) \gg 0.35 \nu/n_f^*$ the relation for absorption coefficient ratio becomes

$$\frac{\mu_{cov}}{\mu_{ion}} = \frac{|M_{if}|_{cov}^2}{|M_{if}|_{ion}^2} = 1 + \frac{0.35 \nu (2n_s + 2)}{(Z_s - S_s) n_f^*} \quad (10)$$

Equation (9) and (10) very clearly establish that when a bond becomes less ionic (or more covalent) the edge absorption coefficient should also increase.

In fact, equation (9) could be generalised as

$$\frac{\mu_{cov}}{\mu_{ion}} = \frac{Z_s - S_s - S_0}{Z_s - S_s - S} \quad (11)$$

where, S_0 like S is the screening factor (screening divided by n_f^*) arising due to known covalency of $M-L$ bond in a standard whose edge absorption coefficient is μ_{ion} . S_0 is zero for ideally ionic $M-L$ bond. The degeneracies of the final states, however, do not affect equation (11) or other previous expressions. It may further be noted from equations (6) and (9) that $Z_s - S_s$ is systematically smaller for initial states of lower quantum number n_f^* . This further suggests that the effect of covalency on absorption coefficient ratio get amplified by the choice of higher energy initial states, M -edge spectra being more sensitive to covalency than L -edge spectra and being still more sensitive than K -edge spectra.

Two important results of this simple analysis are as follows: (i) increase in bond covalency always brings about an enhancement in the edge absorption intensities and (ii) this effect is more pronounced for initial states of higher quantum numbers. It is therefore possible to use edge spectroscopy to determine covalency of bonding by investigating the absorption coefficients. Before discussing some of the examples, we may wish to note that irrespective of the nature of wavefunctions employed in the analysis, a direct correlation exists between the edge absorption coefficients and the covalency of bonding. Since $|f\rangle$ is essentially atomic in character the measurements monitor the covalency effect using spectroscopic property of the central atom only. Also, the changes occurring in μ measures the totality of the covalency effect of all the ligands. The information obtained from the measurements reflect an average covalency of the $M-L$ bonds. This feature has both advantages and disadvantages. The method does not provide information about covalencies of each individual types of bonds when several types of ligands are present around the central atom. For the same reason it could be advantageous in amorphous materials where only such average bond ionicity information is meaningful.

Some case studies :

We shall briefly consider some examples from studies in glasses. In crystalline NdF_3 , Nd^{III} ion is coordinated to nine fluoride ions and bonding of neodymium to fluorine is considered to be completely ionic. However, when NdF_3 is added to BeF_2 glass neodymium cannot be expected to maintain its large coordination number. A lower coordination number is very likely for neodymium in the glasses. But the value should still be higher than that of beryllium (equal to four) since Nd^{III} ions are unlikely to substitute for Be^{II} ions in the glass. EXAFS studies¹⁸ have confirmed these features indicating that neodymium has a coordination number of seven in these glasses. The decreased coordination is also associated with a small decrease in the $Nd-F$

Fig. 2. Normalised L_{III} -edge spectrum of Nd^{III} : (a) in glass (NdF_3 - BeF_3) and (b) in crystalline NdF_3 (normalisation procedure may be seen in Ref. 13).

Fig. 3. Normalised L_{III} -edge spectra of Th^{IV} : (a) in crystalline ThF_4 and (b) in ThF_4 - HfF_4 glass.

distance which again indicates enhanced covalency of Nd-F bonding. One should, therefore, expect this increase to be reflected in the edge absorption coefficients of neodymium in NdF_3 - BeF_3 glass.

Neodymium L_{III} -edge spectra is shown in Fig. 2. For both crystalline NdF_3 and NdF_3 - BeF_3 glass, L_{III} -edge arises from $2p \rightarrow 5d$ ($^2P_{3/2} \rightarrow ^3D_{5/2}$) transition in neodymium at an edge energy of 6208.0 eV. When Nd-F bonds become covalent it corresponds to a reverse transfer of charge from fluorine to neodymium which puts back electron density in the 4f levels of neodymium. Such 4f electrons screen the 5d level (the final state for the L_{III} -edge) and hence, the absorption coefficient increases (Fig. 2). Using appropriate values of screening constants in equation (8) the intensity ratio can be expressed as $\mu_a/\mu_o = 1 + 0.105 \delta$, where δ is the number of electrons involved in covalency. Covalent electrons amounts to $(\delta/3) \times 100\%$ covalency (assuming that all the three electrons of neodymium are involved in covalent bonding for 100% covalency). Experi-

mental value of $(\mu_{glass}/\mu_{crystal})$ is equal to 1.15 (evaluated on the basis of the areas under the normalised absorption coefficient peaks) and it may be easily seen that the covalency should be of the order of 50% in the glass (perhaps a high estimate). The significant point of this analysis is that bonding in glass definitely becomes considerably more covalent.

A similar analysis has been performed in ThF_4 - HfF_4 glasses¹⁰. The L_{III} -edge absorption coefficient of thorium at 16.3 keV in the glass (composition: 0.33 ThF_4 , 0.67 HfF_4) and in crystalline ThF_4 are shown in Fig. 3. A significant feature of this glass is that the coordination numbers of thorium in the glass and in the crystal are equal, and equal to eight. The absorption coefficient ratios were found to be about 1.06 which suggest that Th-F bond is about 30% more covalent in the glasses.

Another example which is illustrative of the use of the absorption coefficient analysis in bonding studies is provided by the lead oxyhalide glass

PbO.PbX_2 ($X=\text{F, Cl}$). L_1 -edge absorption of lead has been used to demonstrate that the average ionicity of lead-ligand bond decreases in the oxyhalide glasses as a function of PbX_2 concentration. On the basis of other structural investigations it was established that lead is always bonded to two oxygens and four halide²⁰⁻²² ions in the entire glass-forming compositions. It is to be expected, however, that PbX_2 -rich compositions should be more ionic because PbF_2 and PbCl_2 are typically ionic materials while PbO is a highly covalent compound²³. Such a change in the covalency of the average lead-ligand bond has immediate consequences on the geometry of $[\text{PbO}_2\text{X}_4]$ units. In fact, we have shown elsewhere²³ that the symmetry of the $[\text{PbO}_2\text{F}_4]$ octahedra changes all the way from $C_2 \rightarrow C_{2v} \rightarrow D_{4h}$ as PbF_2 concentration in the glass is increased. The more symmetrical arrangement of the ligands require a pronounced increase in the ionicity of the lead-ligand bond. Completely covalently bonded $[\text{PbO}_2\text{F}_4]$ unit corresponds to the presence of ten electrons in the bonding orbitals of which we assume five electrons would be involved in shielding the final d states of the L_1 -edge absorption. In the purely ionic compositions there would be only two electrons in lead valence level corresponding to Pb^{II} ion. The extremes of ionicity (0% and 100%) therefore corresponds to shielding by five and two electrons respectively in the (6s, 6p) valence shell of lead. The absorption coefficient, μ_{L_1} , is given by

$$\mu_{L_1} = (K\omega_{L_1} a^2) / [b + cg]^{12.4} \quad (12)$$

where, K , a , b and c are constants, $K = (4\pi e^2 / nc)$, $a = \Gamma(6.2) = 169.41$, $b = 39.622$ and $c = 0.313$, and g is the number of electrons involved in covalency which varies between 0 and 3. Variation of μ_{L_1} is shown as a function of g in Fig. 4a, where μ is given in

units of K . In Fig. 4b variation of the absorption coefficients of the L_1 -edge is also shown for comparison. The trends appear quite satisfactory. No absolute comparisons have, however, been made.

Concluding remarks :

A case has been made here to show that covalency effect can be monitored through the absorption coefficient measurements associated with X-ray edge absorptions. The advantage of such a method is that ligand properties do not enter the analysis. Ionicity is quantified through a direct evaluation of the effective electron density causing additional screening. Electrons involved in covalent bonding do not affect the formal valence state of the atom. In a more systematic study, it should be possible to generate plots of absorption coefficients *versus* percentage covalencies of bonding for a given atom in its different formal valence states. Covalencies of unknown bonding situations may then in principle be determined through interpolation. Bonding in pure metal (preferably in vapour state) and in free ions (preferably in dilute solutions in indifferent solvents) may be used to generate the extreme points on such a plot. Covalencies determined by interpolation in such plots can be much more reliable than estimates obtained from simple electronegativity differences. Further, determination of edge absorption coefficients should also be quite simple particularly with the availability of intense and highly polarised light sources at synchrotron facilities.

Equation (11) can be cast into a more elegant form, if we consider μ_{ion} as the edge absorption coefficient of the free ions (or as suggested before, absorption coefficients in dilute solutions of inert

Fig. 4. (a) Variation of L_1 -edge absorption coefficient of Pb^{II} as a function of the number of covalent electrons. (b) Variation of the experimental L_1 -edge absorption coefficients of Pb^{II} in PbO-PbF_2 glasses as a function of PbF_2 concentration.

solvents). If we substitute $a = (Z_p - S_p)$ in equation (11),

$$(\mu_{\text{cov}}/\mu_{\text{ion}}) = a/(a - S) \quad (13)$$

Equation (13) can be further simplified by taking logarithms and expanding $\ln(1 \pm z) \approx \pm z$ so that

$$\ln(\mu_{\text{cov}}/\mu_{\text{ion}}) \approx S/a$$

or more simply,

$$\mu_{\text{cov}} = \mu_{\text{ion}} \exp(S/a) \quad (14)$$

Thus, a log linear relation exists between additional screening by the covalent electrons and the edge absorption coefficients. Further, the slope $1/a$ is characteristic of the quantum number of initial states and is higher for higher values of n_i . $1/a$ may be considered as an amplification parameter. Measurements of X-ray edge absorption coefficients may thus provide a veritable tool to study covalency effects in bonding.

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